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THE DISCIPLINE PERSONAL FINANCE AND STUDENTS' FINANCIAL HABITS FROM THIS COURSE

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ABSTRACT

The general objective of this study was to measure the impact of disciplines linked to Education Financial in the financial habits of its students. The importance of this study was given in comparison of the financial habits of students taking Financial Education courses with you what no to the are studying. It was treated of one study descriptive, of nature basic, with qualitative and quantitative approaches, using research as a technical procedure field by applying a questionnaire with closed questions to 9th period students of the undergraduate course in Accounting Sciences at UFRJ and to students of other courses graduation, with the aim of detecting in these students the ability to recognize and manipulate key concepts in finance, as well as identifying your financial attitudes in practice in relation to risk and consumption. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with the teacher from the discipline "Finance Personal" of course of Graduation of Sciences Accounting and your coordinators.